

SCHOOL HEADS' LEVEL OF PREPAREDNESS AND COMPETENCY ON LITERACY REMEDIATION PROGRAM (LRP) IMPLEMENTATION: BASIS FOR POLICY RECOMMENDATION

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of preparedness and competency of public elementary school heads in the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) in the Division of Bataan and to examine their significant relationship to program implementation. A quantitative descriptive-correlational research method was utilized. Purposive sampling was employed to select the 37 school heads who responded to the survey. A researcher-developed questionnaire was used to gather data. The instrument was content-validated and pilot tested for reliability. Preparedness was determined in terms of policy knowledge, training participation, and resource allocation. Competency was measured in the delivery of technical assistance, implementation of monitoring and evaluation, and engagement of stakeholders. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed in analyzing the data. Frequency percentage mean, and standard deviation were used as descriptive statistics. Pearson correlation and multiple regression were used as inferential statistics with a significance level of 0.05. One of the results was that school heads, on average, exhibited high preparedness and competency levels in all areas. Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) implementation was also evaluated as being highly compliant and of high process quality. Besides, statistical results indicated that preparedness factors were notably associated with competency factors and amongst these, resources allocation was the one showing the strongest connection. Such results imply that the preparedness and competency of school heads are crucial factors for the success of the implementation of the program.

Keywords: *Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), school heads' preparedness, leadership competency, instructional leadership, program implementation, public elementary schools*

INTRODUCTION

Foundational reading skills are essential literacy development components. They include phonological awareness, knowledge of the alphabet, phonics, and spelling (Lindsey, 2024). Learners must master these basics to become successful readers, as reading comprehension is equally important skill, as reading without understanding delays learning. However, for many learners, mastering these foundational skills remains a significant challenge in the Philippines. The Philippine Statistics Authority's Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey (FLEMMS) says that 24 million Filipinos between the ages of 10 and 64 are functionally illiterate, and 5.8 million of them are basically illiterate (EDCOM 2, 2025).

This failure to establish foundational skills during the critical early years (0-8 years) contributes to significant, system-wide challenges in basic education in the Philippines (UNESCO, 2021). Across the Philippine education system, teaching reading and literacy remains a primary problem. This is further supported by a DepEd report that out of 1.7 million Grade 3 students, 60, 000 learners had not yet mastered phonics skills like the letter sounds and simple word recognition at a grade 1 level. These learners are categorized as "Low Emergent Readers," meaning they have difficulties with fundamental reading skills, such as blending sounds to form words, recognizing letters and their sounds, and decoding simple words. Internationally, The World Bank's Global Report (2022) says that 70% of 10-year-olds in low-and middle-income countries cannot read and understand a text that is appropriate for their age. This is a big jump from 57% in 2019, which shows the devastating impact of COVID-19 related school closures and disruptions on foundational learning. These findings point out the urgency of implementing effective literacy intervention within the school system.

Studies show that early mastery of foundational reading skills especially phonemic awareness, phonics, and decoding is highly correlated with later academic success and school completion, while well-structured teaching methods lead to significantly better literacy results in the beginning stages of education (Jones et al., 2025). Moreover, parental involvement and support in foundational literacy development have been identified as significant contributors to early reading success of children, implying that both school and home environments play important roles in literacy acquisition (Srinivas, 2025).

In response to this problem, Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) was implemented through DepEd Memorandum No. 34, s. 2025 by the Department of Education (2025). The program offers intensive structured research-based approaches to support struggling readers. The program places emphasis on improving learner's reading proficiency through small-group sessions, continuous monitoring of progress, and targeted instructions. Though the program provides a comprehensive framework for literacy improvement, its success depends on effective implementation at the school level.

A significant factor in the success of education programs is the contribution of school leaders, particularly in the context of instructional leadership. Studies have shown that

school leaders are key drivers of teaching and learning as they guide the implementation of curriculum, supervise teaching and learning, and strengthen teacher growth (Pietsch et al. 2023; He et al. 2024). Two main factors of leadership that affect the implementation of policies are the school leaders' preparedness and competency. Preparedness indicates school leaders' familiarity with knowledge and their capability in planning, as well as managing resources, whereas competency is the set of leadership skills required for facilitating technical assistance, conducting monitoring and evaluation, and getting stakeholders involved. These leadership skills are a prime necessity for effective leadership in schools and are based on instructional leadership principles that stress supervision, making decisions on the basis of data, and constant improvement of teaching methods (Caritativo & Fernandez, 2025). Besides that, school effectiveness is heavily influenced by the quality of instruction, which is the main focus of school leaders as they work towards creating a collaborative learning environment, as noted by instructional leadership theory (Arambala, 2025).

Existing studies point a significant role of school leadership in enhancing literacy results. However, there is limited empirical evidence examining how school heads' preparedness and competency influence the implementation of literacy remediation programs, especially in the local context of the Division of Bataan. Many studies focus on teacher-related intervention, leaving a gap in understanding the leadership aspect of program implementation.

Hence, this study addresses this gap by determining the level of preparedness and competency of school heads and their relationship to the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program. The results of this research aimed to provide evidenced-based insights that may inform policy development and strengthen leadership practices in literacy program implementation.

Research Questions

1. How may the profile of the school head be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 years of experience as a school head
 - 1.2 highest educational attainment
 - 1.3 relevant training/seminar attendance related to LRP?
2. What is the level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of:
 - 2.1 policy knowledge
 - 2.2 training attendance
 - 2.3 resource allocation and utilization?
3. What is the level of competency of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of:
 - 3.1 provision of technical assistance and coaching tutors
 - 3.2 monitoring and evaluation of the program
 - 3.3 stakeholder engagements and support mobilization?
4. What is the level of implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) in the public elementary schools, in terms of:

- 4.1 compliance rates
- 4.2 process quality
- 5. Is there any significant impact of the school heads' level of preparedness and competency on the implementation of the LRP?
- 6. Based on the findings of the study, what policy recommendations can be proposed to improve the school heads' preparedness and competency on the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP)?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to determine the level of preparedness and competency of public elementary school heads in the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) in the Division of Bataan. This design is appropriate for describing variables and examining relationships among them using statistical analysis.

The respondents of this study were 37 selected elementary public-school heads in the Division of Bataan who are involved actively in the implementation and supervision of the LRP in the current school year. The respondents varied in terms of educational attainment, years of experience, and related training attended. The study focuses mainly on those who are actively involved in the implementation and supervision of the Literacy Remediation Program. The data provides a comprehensive profile for analysis of leadership preparedness and competency. Moreover, the selection of the respondents is through the use of the purposive sampling technique. This method was used because it allows the researcher to select respondents based on the criteria related to the objective of the study.

The research instrument utilized in this study was a research-made survey questionnaire developed by the researcher. It was designed to gather data on school heads' preparedness, competency, and implementation of the LRP. The tool was arranged into five main parts based on the study's conceptual framework. In the first part, this section gathers descriptive data on school heads. For the second part, the preparedness of the school heads, focusing on policy knowledge, training attendance, and resource allocation. The third part measures competence in terms of providing technical assistance, coaching for tutors, and involving stakeholders. Finally, the fourth part is about how well the program is being followed, including the duration of the program, the number of groups, and the quality monitoring process. All parts comprise 6 items each. Each item was measured using a Likert-type scale, ranging from 4 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree).

In order to verify the content validity, the instrument was crafted and then referred to a panel of experts for their assessment and opinions. The panel of experts was asked to assess the instruments from the viewpoint of the clarity, relevance, coherence, construct validity, and alignment with research questions. The experts' feedback was obtained through a validation checklist and a rating form. After content validation, pilot testing was

conducted among a small group of school heads who were not part of the actual study sample. The pilot test helped identify the clarity of items, consistency of responses, estimated time to complete the questionnaire, and overall usability of the instrument. The data gathered from the pilot test was analyzed for reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Items with low item-total correlation or those that affected the reliability coefficient were assessed and modified or deleted as needed. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 and above was acceptable for the instrument.

The data collection process for this quantitative study was a systematic sequence to collect quantitative data on the school heads' level of preparedness and competency in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). Before collecting the data, the researcher sought the approval from the graduate school adviser and research panel. Then a formal letter of request was sent to the School Division Office of Bataan to request permission to carry out the study among public elementary school heads. After the approval, communication was established with the district supervisor and school heads about the schedule and mode of data collection.

The validated survey questionnaire was administered to the selected respondents. With the cover letter, the researcher explained the study's purpose, explained that participation was voluntary, assured the confidentiality of responses, and provided the instrument's instructions. The questionnaire was handed out either as printed copies or through secure online forms, depending on the accessibility and preference of the respondents. Respondents were given enough time to complete the instrument. When the responses were collected, they were checked for completeness and encoded for statistical analysis.

The data gathered in this study was systematically processed and analyzed to answer the research questions and test the hypothesis. Questionnaire responses were entered into SPSS. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) were utilized to identify preparedness, competency, and LRP implementation levels. Inferential statistics like Pearson correlation and multiple regression were also used to analyze the relationship and the predictive effect of the school heads' preparedness and competency on program implementation at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

This presents the data gathered from the instrument in accordance with specific problem being investigated, the results of the statistical analysis, and interpretation of findings.

Table 1. The profile of the school head be described in terms of years of experience as school head

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	7	18.92
Master's Degree (Units)	19	51.35
Master's Degree (Completed)	9	24.32
Doctorate Degree (Units)	2	5.41
Total	37	100

As seen from this table, the largest group belongs to those with 0-5 years of experience comprising 15 respondents or 40.54%. This is followed by 8 respondents or 21.62% rating who have 16 years and above experience. While the 6-10 years and 11-15 years have the same number of respondents with 7 each and a rating of 18.92%). The data showed a various range of experience levels among the participants involved in the LRP implementation.

Table 2. The profile of the school head be described in terms of highest educational attainment

Years of Experience as a School head	Frequency	Percent
0-5 years	15	40.54
6-10 year	7	18.92
11-15 yea	7	18.92
16 years	8	21.62
Total	37	100

Table 2 presents the educational background of the school heads. Out of 37 respondents most of the school head have earned units in master's degree comprising of (19 or 51.35%) but not yet completed it. This is followed by those who have completed their master's degree with 9 respondents or 24.32%. Meanwhile, 7 school heads hold only a bachelor's degree with percentage of 18.92%, and small portion of school head with units in doctorate degree having a 2 or 5.41%.

Table 3. The profile of the school head be described in terms of relevant training/seminar attendance related to LRP

Relevant Training Attendance	Frequency	Percent
8-16 hours	15	40.54
17-24 hours	11	29.73
25 hours and above	9	24.32
None	2	5.41
Total	37	100

Table 3 present the profile of school heads in terms of their relevant training or seminar attendance related to the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). This table reveals that majority of the school head out of 37 of them have attended training with a duration of 8-16 hours with rating of 15 or 40.54%. While the other 11 respondents got 29.73% who have undergone 17-24 hours of training. Meanwhile, 9 respondents or 24.32% have attended 25 hours and above relevant training. Finally, few of the school head have shown having no attendance in LRP related training with rating or 2 or 5.41%.

Table 4. The level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of policy knowledge

Policy knowledge	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I have thoroughly read and understood the DepEd Memorandum on LRP.	3.54	0.51	Strongly Agree
I clearly understand objectives and target learners of the LRP.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
I am familiar with the required procedures and standards of LRP implementation.	3.44	0.50	Strongly Agree
I can clearly explain LRP guidelines to teachers and tutors.	3.41	0.55	Strongly Agree
I understand the expected outputs and reports required for LRP.	3.54	0.51	Strongly Agree
I can interpret LRP policies and translate them into school level actions.	3.38	0.55	Agree
General Mean and SD	3.48	0.52	Strongly Agree

Table 4 reflects the level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in terms of

policy knowledge in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). The general mean of 3.48 with a standard deviation of 0.52 reveals that the respondents strongly agree that they have enough policy knowledge related to LRP implementation. The highest-rated indicator was the understanding of objectives and targeted learners (M=3.59).

Table 5. The level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of training attendance

Training attendance	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I have attended formal training related to LRP implementation.	3.43	0.77	Strongly Agree
The trainings I attended improved my understanding of literacy remediation.	3.41	0.76	Strongly Agree
I ensure my LRP tutors/teachers attend relevant trainings.	3.41	0.72	Strongly Agree
I initiate school - based echo training or LAC sessions on LRP.	3.19	0.94	Agree
I actively seek additional learning opportunities about literacy intervention.	3.49	0.56	Strongly Agree
Training learnings are applied in our school's LRP planning.	3.54	0.61	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.41	0.73	Strongly Agree

Table 5 displays the level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in terms of training attendance related to the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). As seen in the table, the general mean of 3.41 (SD = 0.73), interpreted as strongly agree. This suggests that they have engaged and benefited from the training attended, showing a high level of preparedness in this aspect.

The highest mean was observed in the application of training learnings in school LRP planning (M=3.54), followed by seeking additional learning opportunities on literacy intervention (M=3.49). On the other hand, the lowest rated indicators were recorded in initiating school-based echo training or LAC session (M=3.19).

Table 6. The level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of resource allocation and utilization

Resource Allocation and Utilization	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Funds are properly allocated to support LRP activities.	3.41	0.64	Strongly Agree
Instructional materials for LRP are sufficiently provided.	3.50	0.61	Strongly Agree
I prioritize LRP need in school resource planning.	3.44	0.61	Strongly Agree
Available resources are efficiently utilized for LRP implementation.	3.46	0.56	Strongly Agree
I mobilize additional resources when LRP materials are lacking.	3.46	0.51	Strongly Agree
Scheduling and staffing adjustments are made to support LRP.	3.43	0.55	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.45	0.58	Strongly Agree

Table 6 exhibits the level of preparedness of public elementary school heads in terms of resource allocation and utilization. The general mean of 3.45 (SD = 0.58) was interpreted as “strongly agree” showing that school heads perceive themselves as ready and prepared in managing and allocating resources to support LR activities.

Additionally, other indicators shows that school heads most strongly agree that instructional materials for LRP are provided sufficiently (M=3.50) and that available resources are utilized efficiently (M=3.46).

Table 7. The level of competency of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of provision of technical assistance and coaching tutors

Provision of Technical Assistance and Coaching	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I regularly provide instructional guidance to LRP tutors.	3.35	0.59	Agree
I conducted coaching conversation with LRP teachers.	3.38	0.59	Agree
I observe LRP sessions and give constructive feedback.	3.41	0.60	Strongly Agree

I help tutors solve instructional difficulties in remediation classes.	3.54	0.61	Strongly Agree
I facilitate LAC sessions focused on literacy remediation strategies.	3.47	0.61	Strongly Agree
My technical assistance improves tutors' instructional practices.	3.49	0.61	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.44	0.60	Strongly Agree

This table presents that public elementary school heads reflect a generally strong level of competency in providing technical assistance and coaching to tutors involved in the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), with a general mean of 3.44 (SD=0.60), interpreted as “Strongly agree”. This suggest that school heads show high engagement in supporting tutors with instructional difficulties (M=3.54) through instructional guidance.

Table 8. The level of competency of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of monitoring and evaluation of the program

Monitoring and Evaluation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I regularly monitor LRP sessions and activities.	3.58	0.55	Strongly Agree
use monitoring tools/checklists for LRP.	3.59	0.55	Strongly Agree
I review learner progress data in LRP.	3.70	0.52	Strongly Agree
Monitoring results are used to improve program delivery.	3.76	0.49	Strongly Agree
I ensure that LRP reports are accurate and submitted on time.	3.68	0.53	Strongly Agree
I conduct periodic evaluation on LRP effectiveness in the school.	3.59	0.55	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.65	0.53	Strongly Agree

The table shows the level of competency of public elementary school heads in terms of monitoring and evaluation. The overall mean rated as 3.65 (SD=0.53), interpreted as “strongly agree” this shows that the school heads always demonstrate a high level of competency in monitoring and evaluating the implementation of LRP. Among the indicators, the highest average was recorded in the implementation of the use of monitoring results to enhance program delivery (M=3.76), followed by reviewing learner progress data (M=3.70) and ensuring accurate and timely submission of reports (M=3.68).

Table 9. The level of competency of public elementary school heads in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), in terms of stakeholder engagements and support mobilization

Stakeholder Engagement and Support Mobilization	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
I engage parents in supporting LRP learners.	3.70	0.46	Strongly Agree
I coordinate with stakeholders to support LRP Resources.	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
I inform the community about LRP goals and activities.	3.57	0.50	Strongly Agree
I build partnerships to strengthen LRP implementation.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
Stakeholders actively participate in LRP-related initiatives.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
I maintain regular communication with stakeholders regarding LRP progress.	3.57	0.50	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.61	0.49	Strongly Agree

Table 9 present that public elementary school heads demonstrate a very high level of competency in the areas of stakeholder engagement and support mobilization. This is evident through the average score of 3. 61 (SD = 0. 49), which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This shows that school heads are not only actively involving stakeholders but also sustaining partnerships to support the rollout of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). With a mean of 3. 70, the highest among all indicators was the engagement of parents in supporting LRP learners. It appears then that parental involvement is a potent area of practice for school heads. Next in line is stakeholder coordination for resources (M = 3. 62), which shows that the school heads, through effective collaboration, were able to mobilize support.

Table 10. The level of implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) in the public elementary schools, in terms of compliance rates

Compliance Rates	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
LRP is implemented according to prescribed duration and schedule.	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
Learner grouping follows LRP guidelines.	3.65	0.48	Strongly Agree

Required LRP instructional materials are available.	3.57	0.55	Strongly Agree
Tutors follow prescribed LRP procedures.	3.65	0.48	Strongly Agree
Assessment requirements of LRP are complied with.	3.62	0.49	Strongly Agree
Reporting requirement of LRP are complied with.	3.59	0.50	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.62	0.50	Strongly Agree

Table 10 shows that the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) by public elementary schools is done with very high compliance. This is evident that overall mean of 3.62 (SD = 0.50). Public elementary schools are following through with the program guidelines, procedures, and requirements consistently. More detailed results such as learner grouping and adherence to prescribed procedures had even higher scores (M = 3.65) indicating that the main implementation work is being done in a very orderly manner. Likewise, the compliance with scheduling, assessment, and reporting requirements (M = 3.59-3.62) reflects a very good level of following through with the program standards.

Although instructional materials attained the lowest mean (M = 3.57); however, it is still considered within the "strongly agree" category, which means there are only very slight gaps in resource provision.

Table 11. The level of implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) in the public elementary schools, in terms of process quality

Process Quality	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Technical assistance provided to tutors is timely and relevant.	3.57	0.50	Strongly Agree
Monitoring activities are consistent and systematic.	3.64	0.49	Strongly Agree
Coaching support improves remediation instruction quality.	3.68	0.47	Strongly Agree
LRP sessions are delivered with instructional fidelity.	3.65	0.54	Strongly Agree
Stakeholders support positively affects LRP delivery.	3.54	0.56	Strongly Agree

Program adjustments are made based on monitoring data.	3.59	0.55	Strongly Agree
General Mean and SD	3.61	0.52	Strongly Agree

As indicated in Table 11 above, the quality of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) implementation process is high since the overall mean is at 3.61 with a standard deviation of 0.52. This means that school heads implement quality processes in their schools. The highest mean was seen in the aspect of coaching support that improves the quality of instruction for remediation (M = 3.68), followed by instructional fidelity (M = 3.65), and consistent monitoring activities (M = 3.64). This implies that school heads implement strong support mechanisms for instruction quality.

The low standard deviation implies that school heads perceive these aspects consistently. Although not as high as the others, aspects such as support from stakeholders (M = 3.54) and technical assistance (M = 3.57) imply that support systems for external sources could be further improved.

Table 12. The significant impact of the school head's level of preparedness in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP)

INDICATORS		Provision of Technical Assistance and Coaching Tutors	Monitoring and Evaluation of The Program	Stakeholder Engagements and Support Mobilization	Decision	Remarks
Policy Knowledge	ρ	0.657*	0.582*	0.488*	Significant	Ho is rejected
	p-value	<0.001	<0.001	0.002		
Training Attendance	ρ	0.656*	0.446*	0.631*	Significant	Ho is rejected
	p-value	<0.001	0.006	<0.001		
Resource Allocation and Utilization	ρ	0.874*	0.723*	0.702*	Significant	Ho is rejected
	p-value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001		

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 12 illustrates the significant effect of the school heads' level of preparedness and competency in the implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). The results show that all the school heads' preparedness and competency variables are correlated with the various components of the Literacy Remediation Program implementation, as indicated by the Spearman rho correlation values, which are all below the 0.05 level of significance, as shown in the table above. Policy knowledge has a strong

correlation with the provision of technical assistance and coaching tutors, monitoring and evaluation of the program, and stakeholder engagement and support mobilization, as indicated by the Spearman rho correlation values of 0.657, 0.582, and 0.488, respectively, all of which are below the 0.05 level of significance, as shown in the table above. Likewise, attendance at training shows a significant relationship with the provision of technical assistance and coaching tutors ($\rho = 0.656$, $p < 0.001$), monitoring and evaluation ($\rho = 0.446$, $p = 0.006$), and stakeholder engagement and support mobilization ($\rho = 0.631$, $p < 0.001$).

The results showed that the more the school heads participate and attend training, the more equipped and empowered they are to effectively and efficiently manage and monitor the program, and to mobilize stakeholders to participate and help in the implementation and sustainment of literacy remediation programs in their respective schools. Furthermore, the moderate to strong significant positive correlation also showed that the more the school heads are provided with and participate in continuous and regular training, the better and more effectively they are equipped and empowered to manage and sustain literacy remediation programs, and to effectively and efficiently monitor and evaluate program implementation, and to mobilize stakeholders to participate and help in the implementation and sustainment of literacy remediation programs in their respective schools. Moreover, the results showed that the allocation and utilization of resources have the strongest significant positive correlation with the provision of technical assistance and coaching tutors ($\rho = 0.874$, $p < 0.001$), monitoring and evaluation ($\rho = 0.723$, $p < 0.001$), and stakeholder engagement and support mobilization ($\rho = 0.702$, $p < 0.001$). The results showed a very strong positive correlation, indicating that the school heads who are good and effective managers and allocators and utilizers of resources are more capable and empowered to effectively and efficiently implement the Literacy Remediation Program.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study provide a detailed picture of how the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) implementation in Bataan executed. The profile of the school heads shows that the leaders are relatively young with 40.54% having on five years of experience or less. Despite their relative lack of experience, the high percentage of master's degree (over 75%) and continuous participation in LRP-related trainings (over 94%) reflect an academically equipped workforce and professionally proactive.

Preparedness is reflected in the "Strongly Agree" ratings in relation to the level of policy knowledge ($M=3.48$) and training attendance ($M=3.41$). These results agree with the concept of instructional leadership that requires leaders to be knowledgeable. The high level of preparedness means that the dissemination of information about DepEd Memorandum No. 34, s. 2025 by the Department of Education was effective. It is observed that the school heads have the highest level of confidence in terms of knowing the objectives and target learners. According to Lindsey (2024), foundational literacy skills are fundamental for all future learning. Failure to identify the "Low Emergent Readers" makes remediation ineffective.

Moreover, monitoring and evaluation competency was found to have high levels, especially when it comes to using the results to improve program implementation (M=3.76). This proves instructional leadership as discussed by Arambala (2025) that suggests data-based decision making as one of the most critical components of school effectiveness. Reviewing the data related to learner performance (M=3.70), school heads in Bataan make an effort to go beyond administrative supervision and proceed instructional leadership. This essential since, according to UNESCO (2021), systematic issues experienced in the Philippines are often the result of poor foundation acquired during early years.

Engagement with different stakeholders (M=3.61) demonstrated high levels as well. Particularly, engaging parents (M=3.70) proved the results obtained by Jones et al. (2025), who emphasized the significance of parental involvement in fostering reading. Thus, a transition from school-based literacy to collaborative family literacy seems to be among priorities set by Bataan school heads to deal with the learning poverty call “the big jump” reported by the World Bank (2022).

The most significant finding from this study is the strong correlation between resource allocation and technical assistance ($r=0.874$). This means that school heads who manage instructional resources and budgets well are better equipped to offer support to their tutors. This correlation shows that the school head plays a dual role of administrator and instructional leader. Moreover, the highly significant correlation among all the factors discussed in Table 12 indicates that preparedness is functional aspect of leadership competence.

In summary, the implementation of the LRP in Bataan shows great compliance and adherence to process standards. The findings of this paper coincide with those in Pietsch et al. (2023) and He et al. (2024) studies. They see school administrators as the major implementers of curriculum development. However, there could be room for improvement as indicated by the slightly low mean for “echo” training (M=3.19). School heads attended national or divisional seminars, but they should also hold more LAC meetings at their respective institutions.

Conclusions

The findings reveal that school head in the public elementary hold varied professional profiles in terms of educational attainment, years of experience, and relevant training relevant to the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP). Most of them are pursuing graduate studies, particularly at the master’s degree level, and large proportion are relatively new in their positions, although a notable number are highly experienced. Majority have attended Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) relevant trainings, though generally within minimal to moderate durations.

School heads demonstrate a high level across policy knowledge, training attendance, and resource allocation and utilization in terms of preparedness. This reflects as consistently high mean ratings interpreted as “strongly agree”. This indicates that in the

implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) they are basically well-prepared, with great understanding of policies, active engagement in professional development, and effective management of resources. In contrast, slight variations in specific indicators suggest minor areas for improvement, particularly in translating policy into practice and strengthening school – based training initiatives.

Likewise, regarding competency, the school heads show a high level of competence in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), particularly in providing technical assistance and coaching, conducting monitoring and evaluation, and engaging stakeholders. As the result shows, monitoring and evaluation recorded the highest level of competency, followed by stakeholder engagement, while technical assistance and coaching, although still high, showed relatively lower mean scores in certain aspects such as regular coaching and instructional guidance.

In terms of compliance rates and process quality both registered as very high in the level of Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) implementation in public elementary school in the Division of Bataan. School always adhere to prescribed guidelines, reporting requirements, and procedures, while also maintaining strong instructional support system, including data-driven program adjustments, monitoring, and coaching.

Moreover, the findings confirm that school heads' level of preparedness has significant positive relationship with their competency in implementing the LRP. All indicators of preparedness – policy knowledge, training attendance, and resource allocation are significantly correlated with key implementation domain, mainly technical assistance, monitoring and evaluation, and stakeholder engagement. Of all these indicators, resource allocation and utilization show the strongest relationship, suggesting its critical role in effective program implementation.

In general, the findings concludes that school heads are generally well-prepared and highly competent, and that their level of preparedness significantly affects the successful implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP).

Recommendations

The findings of this study shows that the profiles of the school head generally varied in terms of educational attainment, years of experience, and training attendance. In this regard, it is recommended that policies be developed to encourage school heads to pursue advance academic studies and equitable access to related Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) trainings, mainly for those with none and limited training attendance and those still completing graduate studies.

Although the findings reveal that school heads demonstrate a high level of preparedness in terms of policy knowledge, training attendance, and resource allocation, it is recommended to keep and sustain these strengths by continuous professional development programs. However, introducing targeted intervention may further enhance competencies in translating policies into school level practices, and the conduct of school-

based initiative training should be improved, such as Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions. Since school heads also demonstrate high level competency in technical assistance, monitoring and evaluation, and stakeholder engagement, it is also recommended that existing support systems should be strengthened and maintained. More so, the improvement consistency in coaching and instructional guidance must be given attention to further enhance support given to teachers and tutors.

Considering both compliance rates and process quality are very high in the level of Literacy Remediation Program (LRP) implementation, it is highly recommended that schools should continue to uphold adherence to program guidelines and standards. However, results identified minor gaps in instructional materials provision and support systems. This may be addressed through improved planning and resource management.

On top of this, as the findings confirm that the school heads' level of preparedness significantly influences their competency in implementing the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP), it is strongly recommended that policies focus on strengthening preparedness indicators, particularly policy understanding, training participation, and resource allocation by structured capacity-building programs, continuous monitoring systems, and sustained funding support. These policy recommendation's objective is to further improve the preparedness and competency of school heads, thus enhancing the overall implementation of the Literacy Remediation Program (LRP).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study strictly observed the ethical standards for research involving human participants. Strict adherence to the ethical standards was observed throughout the data collection process. Participation was on a volunteer basis, informed consent was obtained, and respondents were assured that their identities and answers will be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. The conduct data collection began with obtaining request of permission from the graduate school adviser, research panel, and Schools Division Office of Bataan. Formal permission was granted to use the survey questionnaire among the heads of public elementary schools using an official letter a requesting permission.

Participation in the study was completely voluntary and respondents were informed about the objective of the study, nature of participation, and freedom to withdraw from the research process without penalties through a cover letter. Informed consent was sought from all respondents prior to conducting the survey questionnaire. Anonymity and confidentiality were also strictly followed in the study. No identification of the respondents and other related personal information was revealed. The data collected were kept confidential and would only be used for research purposes.

Finally, the study ensured that neither physical nor psychological harm would be brought upon the respondents. The researcher was honest and upright in data gathering, analysis, and discussion of result.

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